
STUDIES ON THE ANTIMICROBIAL EFFICACY OF *Garcinia kola* (HECKEL) SEEDS AGAINST COUGH-CAUSING ORGANISMS

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ABSTRACT: Cough remains a major symptom of respiratory tract infections (RTIs), many of which are caused by bacterial pathogens that are increasingly resistant to conventional antibiotics. This study investigated the antimicrobial activity of *Garcinia kola* seed extracts against bacteria isolated from cough swab samples. The aim was to scientifically evaluate the traditional use of *Garcinia kola* (bitter kola) in managing respiratory tract infections (RTIs). Bacterial isolates were identified using standard microbiological and biochemical procedures. Extracts of *Garcinia kola* seeds were prepared using aqueous, ethanol, and chloroform solvents. Qualitative phytochemical analysis of the *Garcinia kola* extracts was carried out using standard methods. The antibacterial analysis was done using the agar well diffusion technique. The Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) and Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) of the extracts were determined according to the macro broth dilution technique. The bacterial recovery pattern revealed *Klebsiella pneumoniae* as the most prevalent organism (100%), followed by *Streptococcus pneumoniae* (70%), *Haemophilus influenzae* (60%), and *Staphylococcus aureus* (30%). Phytochemical screening revealed the presence of bioactive compounds, including flavonoids, alkaloids, tannins, saponins, and phenols, with the aqueous extract containing the richest profile. The results of the study showed that the aqueous extract had the highest antimicrobial effect, producing zones of inhibition up to 24 mm for *Streptococcus pneumoniae* and 22 mm for *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. The ethanol and chloroform extracts demonstrated moderate to low activity. Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) and Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) values confirmed that the aqueous extract was effective at 25 mg/ml for both *Streptococcus pneumoniae* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, indicating strong antimicrobial potential. These findings provide scientific evidence supporting the use of *Garcinia kola* in traditional medicine for the treatment of cough and bacterial RTIs. The study highlights the potential of aqueous *Garcinia kola* extract as a promising candidate for the development of plant-based antimicrobial agents.

Keywords: Antimicrobial Efficacy, *Garcinia Kola*, Seeds, Cough-Causing Organisms

INTRODUCTION

Respiratory tract infections (RTIs) remain a major public health concern globally, especially in developing countries where healthcare access and infrastructure are limited (Gibson and Ryan, 2011). Cough is a common clinical manifestation of RTIs and is often caused by microbial pathogens such as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Haemophilus influenzae*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Klebsiella pneumonia* (Morice

et al., 2020). These organisms are known to colonize the upper and lower respiratory tracts, leading to symptoms ranging from mild coughs to severe bronchitis, pneumonia, and other complications (Oduwole et al., 2018).

In recent years, the increasing prevalence of antimicrobial resistance among respiratory pathogens has posed a significant challenge to effective treatment (Ogono et al., 2014). Overuse and misuse of antibiotics have contributed to the emergence of multidrug-resistant strains, diminishing the efficacy of standard antimicrobial therapies (Manourova et al., 2019; Tesi et al., 2022). Consequently, there is a growing demand for alternative remedies, particularly those derived from natural sources with known therapeutic potential and minimal side effects (Tesi, 2022).

Garcinia kola (Heckel), commonly known as bitter kola, is a plant native to West and Central Africa and is traditionally revered for its medicinal properties (Ali et al., 2020; Ezeigbo et al., 2016). In ethnomedicine, the seeds of *Garcinia kola* are commonly chewed to relieve symptoms associated with coughs, colds, and other respiratory illnesses (Dogara et al., 2022). Its use is often attributed to its bitter taste and the presence of several phytochemical constituents with potential pharmacological effects (Idowu et al., 2020).

Previous phytochemical studies on *Garcinia kola* have revealed that its seeds are rich in secondary metabolites such as flavonoids, saponins, tannins, alkaloids, phenolic compounds, and biflavonoids like kolaviron (Adegboye et al., 2022; Banso et al., 2020b). These compounds have been associated with a wide range of biological activities, including antimicrobial, antiviral, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and immune-modulatory properties (Jackie et al., 2014). Several *in vitro* studies have demonstrated the inhibitory effects of *Garcinia kola* extracts on various microbial pathogens, suggesting its potential as an alternative or complementary treatment to conventional antibiotics (Ogunmoyole et al., 2012; Ukaoma et al., 2013).

Despite these promising findings, there is limited scientific data specifically addressing the antimicrobial activity of *Garcinia kola* seeds against organisms that are known to cause cough. Furthermore, the relationship between its traditional use in the treatment of respiratory symptoms and its actual antimicrobial potential remains underexplored. Thus, a systematic study is necessary to bridge this gap and provide empirical support for the therapeutic claims associated with *Garcinia kola*. This study seeks to investigate the antimicrobial efficacy of *Garcinia kola* seed extracts against selected cough-causing organisms. By evaluating the inhibitory effects of the extracts on bacterial isolates obtained from clinical or symptomatic sources, this research aims to contribute to the growing body of evidence supporting the medicinal value of traditional plant remedies.

Cough remains one of the most common symptoms of respiratory tract infections, many of which are caused by bacterial pathogens such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. The growing resistance of these organisms to commonly used antibiotics has made the treatment of such infections increasingly difficult and less effective. Although *Garcinia kola* seeds are traditionally used to treat coughs, there is limited scientific evidence supporting their effectiveness against bacteria responsible for respiratory infections. With rising antibiotic resistance, it is important to investigate the antimicrobial potential of natural remedies like *Garcinia kola* to validate their traditional use and explore their possible role in modern medicine.

This study aimed to evaluate the antimicrobial efficacy of *Garcinia kola* (Heckel) seed extracts against selected bacterial organisms associated with cough.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

The materials and equipment used for this research were autoclave, incubator, microscope, Bunsen burner, inoculating loop, test tubes, test tubes rack, deep freezer, media, conical flask, hot air oven, petri dish, forceps, spatula, beaker, test tubes racks, weighing balance, measuring cylinder, cough swabs from patients, and *Garcinia kola* (Heckel) seed. Media used included Blood Agar, MacConkey Agar, Eosin Methylene Blue (EMB) Agar, Mannitol Salt Agar (MSA), and Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (SDA). Reagents used included Gram stain reagents, distilled water, dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO), ethanol, peptone water, crystal violet, safranin, lugol's iodine, normal saline, ethanol, Kovac's reagent, and hydrogen peroxide.

Sources of Materials

A total of ten (10) swab samples were collected from consenting cough patients attending University of Nigeria Teaching Hospital (UNTH), Ituku-Ozalla, Enugu state, Nigeria, for isolation of bacteria causing cough. Fresh seeds of *Garcinia kola* were purchased from Eke Agbani Market at Nkanu-West LGA, Enugu state, Nigeria. The seeds were identified by a botanist in the Department of Applied Biology and Biotechnology, ESUT, Nigeria. All reagents, media, chemicals, and equipment used for this study were supplied by the Laboratory section of the Department of Applied Microbiology and Brewing, ESUT.

Pre-treatment of *Garcinia kola* (Heckel) Seed

The *Garcinia kola* were thoroughly washed, screened to remove foreign bodies, and placed into a neatly washed and dried tray. The *Garcinia kola* were dried at room temperature and crushed to coarse powder using a neatly washed local mortar and pestle. The powdered form of the *Garcinia kola* was placed in different containers and were properly labelled and stored.

Preparation of Extracts

Extraction was done using distilled water, methanol, and ethanol through room evaporation. One hundred grams (100g) of dried ground *Garcinia kola* powder was dissolved in 500 mL each of distilled water, methanol, and ethanol for 48 hours. The mixtures were filtered separately using Whatman's filter paper No. 1 to obtain a solution free of solids. The filtrate was evaporated under reduced pressure. The concentrated extract was stored in a labelled sterile screw capped bottle at 2- 8°C.

Phytochemical Analysis

The analysis determines the biologically active compounds that are present in the *Garcinia kola*: alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, saponins, steroids, phenols, tannins, terpenoids, and resins were tested using standard procedures.

Test for Alkaloid (Wagner's test)

Two milliliters (2ml) of each extract was added to a test tube, followed by the addition of 3 drops of Wagner's reagent (Iodine in Potassium iodide). The mixture was heated for 20 minutes using a water bath. The formation of brown precipitate was observed.

Test for Flavonoids (Alkaline Test)

Five milliliters (5ml) of dilute NH₃ solution was added to 1ml of each extract before the addition of concentrated sulphuric acid in a test tube. The formation of yellow precipitate indicated the presence of flavonoids.

Test for Glycoside (Keller Killian's Test)

Ten milliliters (10ml) of 50% tetraoxosulphate (vi) acid was added to 1ml of each extract in a separate test tube, and the mixture was heated gently for 15 minutes, followed by the addition of 10ml of Fehling solution. A brick red precipitate indicated the presence of a Glycoside.

Test for Saponins (Foam test)

Five milliliters (5ml) of each extract was dispensed in a test tube, and 5ml of distilled water was added and shaken vigorously. Persistent froth (foam) that lasted for about 10 minutes indicated the presence of saponins.

Test for Steroid (Salwoski's Test)

Two milliliters (2ml) of each extract was mixed with 2ml of acetic acid in a test tube, and the solution was kept in ice for cooling. Two (2) ml of concentrated Tetraoxosulphate (vi) acid (H_2SO_4) and 1ml of chloroform were added carefully. Color change from violet to blue/bluish green indicated the presence of steroids.

Test for Tannin (Ferric Chloride Test)

Two milliliters (2ml) of each extract was measured into a test tube, and it was heated. About 3 to 4 drops of 10% ferric chloride solution were added to each extract. The formation of a greenish black coloration, which indicated the presence of tannins, was observed and recorded.

Test for Terpenoids

About 5ml of each extract was added with 2ml of chloroform and 3ml of concentrated Tetraoxosulphate (vi) acid (Salwoki test). Reddish brown colour of the interface indicates the presence of Terpenoids.

Test for Phenols (Ferric Chloride)

About 0.1g of each extract was boiled with distilled water and then filtered. To 2ml of each filtrate, a few drops of 10% ferric chloride solution were then added. A green-blue or violet colouration signifies the presence of a phenolic hydroxyl group.

Test for Resins

About 5ml of the extract was added to 5ml of copper acetate solution. The mixture was agitated vigorously and allowed to separate. The appearance of a reddish- brown precipitate indicated the presence of resins.

Media Preparation

The powdered form of all the media used was prepared according to the manufacturer's instructions.

Bacteriological Analysis of the Sample

In the Microbiology Laboratory, the swab samples were streaked directly on already prepared agar plates: Blood agar, MacConkey agar (MA), Eosin Methylene Blue (EMB) Agar, and Mannitol salt agar (MSA). The samples were incubated inverted at room temperature ($37^{\circ}C$) for 24 hours. The cultures were examined periodically for microbial growth and the results were recorded accordingly.

Following incubation, distinct colonies were sub-cultured onto fresh Blood agar, MacConkey agar (MA), Eosin Methylene Blue (EMB) Agar, and Mannitol salt agar (MSA) plates for proper preliminary identification. Purified isolates were stored in nutrient agar slants for further studies. The morphological appearances of the organisms were recorded. The isolates were further subjected to other identification tests. Bacterial isolates were characterized based on their Gram stain reaction and biochemical tests (catalase, indole, and sugar fermentation tests), and identification was made according to Bergey's Manual of Determinative Bacteriology.

Preparation of Inoculum

A loopful of isolated colonies of each bacterial strain stored on nutrient agar slant was taken and inoculated into 4 ml of peptone water, and then incubated at 37°C for 4 h. The concentration of the bacterial suspension was then adjusted with peptone water to obtain a turbidity visually comparable to that of a 0.5 McFarland standard prepared by mixing 0.5 ml of 1.75% (w/v) barium chloride dihydrate ($\text{BaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) with 99.5 ml of 1% (v/v) sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4). This turbidity is equivalent to approximately $1 - 2 \times 10^8$ colony-forming units per ml (CFU/ml). This activated culture was then used as an inoculum for further testing.

Preparation of Garcinia kola Extracts for Antibacterial Assay

A total of 0.8g of each of the Garcinia kola extracts (aqueous, ethanol and methanol) was dissolved in 4ml of dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) to give a concentration of 200mg/ml (stock extract) which was serially diluted to give different concentrations of 100mg/ml, 50mg/ml, 25mg/ml and 12.5mg/ml respectively. The tubes containing the different concentrations of the Garcinia kola extracts were labelled accordingly, and the concentrations were used for the sensitivity test, while an antibiotic (gentamycin) was used as the standard drug control.

Antibacterial Evaluation

The antibacterial effects of the Garcinia kola extracts were determined using the agar well diffusion method according to Zulfa et al. (2016). After modifying the inoculum suspension's turbidity, sterile cotton swabs were inserted into several test tubes holding the isolated bacterial species. Just above the fluid level, the sterile cotton swab was firmly pressed up against the test tube walls. The swab was spun in order to eliminate extra fluid. Following that, each swab was streaked across the whole surface of the different agar plates (Muller-Hinton agar) under aseptic conditions and appropriately spread with a sterile swab stick. After spreading the culture, 6 holes of 6mm in diameter were bored on the plates by using a sterile cork borer. The wells were opened with the help of sterile forceps. Using a sterile micropipette and under sterile conditions, the Garcinia kola extracts were pipetted and dispensed 1ml each into five (5) wells made in the different plates containing the isolated bacteria species, while the standard drug dextromethorphan (40mg/mL) was introduced into the sixth hole for each plate. It was left to stand so that the Garcinia kola extracts and control poured into the holes can diffuse into the agar culture appropriately, after which it was incubated at 37 °C for 24–72hours. The plates were later examined for zones of inhibition after 24 hours of incubation. The diameter of inhibition zones was measured in millimetres with the aid of a ruler and recorded.

Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC)

The MIC of the extracts was determined according to the macro broth dilution method. Standardized suspensions of the test organism were inoculated into a series of sterile tubes of nutrient broth containing two-fold dilutions of Garcinia kola extracts and incubated at 37°C for 24 h. The MICs were read as the lowest concentration that inhibited the growth of the test organisms. The lowest or least concentration of the extract that shows no growth in the test tubes is the MIC of the extract tested.

Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC)

The MBCs were determined by first selecting tubes that showed no growth during MIC determination; a loopful from each tube was sub-cultured onto already gelled nutrient agar plates using the spread plate technique and incubated for 24 h at 37 °C. The least concentration, at which no growth was observed, was noted as the MBC.

Results

Table 1 shows that the aqueous, ethanol, and methanol extracts of *Garcinia kola* seeds contain key phytochemicals such as flavonoids, tannins, saponins, alkaloids, phenols, and glycosides. Table 2 outlined the identification of four major cough-causing pathogens: *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Haemophilus influenzae*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*. *K. pneumoniae* was found in all samples (100%), followed by *S. pneumoniae* (70%), *H. influenzae* (60%), and *S. aureus* (30%) as detailed in Table 3. Table 4 further showed that *K. pneumoniae* made up 38.9% of isolates, while *S. pneumoniae* accounted for 30.6%. Tables 5 and 6 revealed that the aqueous extract had the strongest antibacterial effect, with inhibition zones up to 24 mm and dose-dependent activity. No inhibition was observed at 12.5 mg/ml. MIC results (Table 7) indicated that bacterial growth was inhibited at 25 mg/ml, with full bactericidal activity only at concentrations ≥ 25 mg/ml for the aqueous extract. Ethanol and chloroform extracts were less effective, requiring higher concentrations for similar effects (Table 8)

Table 1: Phytochemical Analysis of the *Garcinia kola* Extracts

Phytochemical Components	Aqueous Extract	Ethanol Extract	Methanol Extract
Alkaloid	++	++	+
Flavonoid	+++	+++	+++
Saponin	+++	++	++
Steroid	—	—	—
Tannin	++	+++	++
Glycoside	++	+	+
Terpenoid	+	++	+
Resins	—	+	+
Phenol	++	++	++

Key: + = slightly present, ++ = moderately present, +++ = abundantly present — = absent

Table 2: Morphology, Microscopic and Biochemical Characteristics of the Bacterial Isolates

Colonial Morphology	Microscopy/Gram reaction	Biochemical Tests							Probable Organism
		Ca	Ind	Sugar fermentation					
				G	L	S	F	M	
Golden-yellow, clusters, small colony with smooth surface on MacConkey agar.	Gram-positive coccus, which appears as grape-like clusters	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
Small, glistening, and grayish-white colonies on Blood agar.	Gram-positive coccus, which appears as grape-like clusters	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i>
Small, pinpoint, translucent, convex, or flat colonies	gram-negative, rod-shaped, asporogenous, and	+	+	+	+	-	+	-	<i>Haemophilus influenzae</i>

colonies on Blood agar. monoflagellated bacterium
 Pink mucoid colonies on EMB agar Gram-negative, + - + + + - + Klebsiella pneumoniae
 non-motile, encapsulated, rod-shaped bacterium.

Key: Ca= catalase test, Ind= Indole test, G = glucose, L = lactose, S = sucrose, F = fructose, M = maltose, + = Positive, - = Negative.

Table 3: Frequency of Occurrence of Identified Bacterial Isolates of Cough Swabs

Bacterial Isolates	Total Swabs	Occurrence	Percentage Occurrence (%)
Staphylococcus aureus	10	3	30
Streptococcus pneumoniae	10	7	70
Haemophilus influenzae	10	6	60
Klebsiella pneumoniae	10	10	100

Table 4: Recovery Pattern of Bacterial Isolates of Cough Swabs

Bacterial Isolates	Recovery Pattern (%)
Staphylococcus aureus	4(11.1%)
Streptococcus pneumoniae	11(30.6%)
Haemophilus influenzae	7(19.4%)
Klebsiella pneumoniae	14(38.9%)
Total	36(100%)

Table 5: Antibacterial Activities of Garcinia kola Extracts on Klebsiella pneumoniae

Garcinia kola Extracts at Different Concentrations (mg/ml)	Zone of Inhibition (mm)		
	Aqueous Extract	Ethanol Extract	Chloroform Extract
200	22	16	15
100	15	11	9
50	11	8	6
25	6	2	1
12.5	—	—	—
Dextromethorphan control (drug control)	25	20	17.00

Table 6: Antibacterial Activities of Garcinia kola Extracts on Streptococcus pneumoniae

Garcinia kola Extracts at Different Concentrations (mg/ml)	Zone of Inhibition (mm)		
	Aqueous Extract	Ethanol Extract	Chloroform Extract
200	24	19	18
100	21	14	12
50	13	10	7
25	7	4	2
12.5	—	—	—
Dextromethorphan (drug control)	26	21	19

Table 7: Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) of Garcinia kola Extracts on Selected Cough Isolates

Garcinia kola Extracts at Different Concentrations (mg/ml)	Klebsiella pneumoniae			Streptococcus pneumoniae		
	Aqueous Extract	Ethanol Extract	Chloroform Extract	Aqueous Extract	Ethanol Extract	Chloroform Extract
200	—	—	—	—	—	—
100	—	—	—	—	—	—
50	—	—	—	—	—	—
25	+	—	—	+	—	—
12.5	+	+	+	+	+	+

Table 8: Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) of Garcinia kola Extracts on Selected Cough Isolates

Garcinia kola Extracts at Different Concentrations (mg/ml)	Klebsiella pneumoniae			Streptococcus pneumoniae		
	Aqueous Extract	Ethanol Extract	Chloroform Extract	Aqueous Extract	Ethanol Extract	Chloroform Extract
200	—	—	—	—	—	—
100	—	—	—	—	—	—
50	—	—	—	—	—	—
25	—	—	—	—	—	—
12.5	+	—	—	+	—	—

Discussion

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the antimicrobial potential of Garcinia kola seed extracts against selected bacterial isolates commonly associated with cough. The results obtained provide clear scientific support for the traditional use of bitter kola in the treatment of respiratory ailments, especially in sub-Saharan Africa, where access to modern antibiotics is sometimes limited.

The phytochemical screening of *Garcinia kola* extracts (Table 4.1) revealed the presence of numerous bioactive compounds, with flavonoids, tannins, phenols, and saponins being prominent. These secondary metabolites have been widely documented in previous studies (Adegboye et al., 2018; Amala et al., 2021; Emmanuel et al., 2022) to possess antimicrobial properties. The abundance of flavonoids and saponins in particular may explain the strong antimicrobial activity observed in the aqueous extract. Their mechanism of action includes disruption of microbial cell walls, inhibition of nucleic acid synthesis, and interference with microbial enzymes.

Isolation and biochemical identification of the pathogens (Table 4.2) confirmed the presence of *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Haemophilus influenzae*, and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, organisms well known for their role in respiratory infections and persistent cough. These organisms have also been isolated by previous researchers (Brook, 2011; Nadia et al., 2013; Uhumwangho and Okolie, 2014) as cough-causing bacteria. The prevalence data (Tables 4.3 and 4.4) indicated that *K. pneumoniae* was the most frequently isolated organism (100%), followed by *S. pneumoniae* (70%). This pattern reflects a trend seen in urban clinical settings in Nigeria, where *K. pneumoniae* has increasingly emerged as a dominant respiratory pathogen, possibly due to poor sanitation and rising antimicrobial resistance.

The antimicrobial assays (Tables 4.5 and 4.6) clearly showed that all three solvent extracts, aqueous, ethanol, and chloroform, exhibited inhibitory activity against the test organisms, with inhibition zones increasing proportionally to extract concentration. However, the aqueous extract consistently produced the highest zones of inhibition, followed by ethanol and chloroform extracts. This suggests that the active compounds in *Garcinia kola* are more soluble or more stable in polar solvents like water, making the aqueous extract the most effective preparation for antimicrobial use.

Interestingly, while the standard antibiotic control (dextromethorphan) exhibited greater antimicrobial activity overall, the zones of inhibition from aqueous extracts were comparable at higher concentrations (200 mg/ml). This observation reinforces the notion that traditional remedies, when properly prepared, can provide moderate antimicrobial effects that are scientifically verifiable.

Further validation of these findings came from the MIC and MBC studies (Tables 4.7 and 4.8), which revealed that the aqueous extract had the lowest MIC and MBC values, indicating strong antimicrobial potency. The extract effectively inhibited growth at 25 mg/ml and demonstrated bactericidal activity at this same concentration, whereas the ethanol and chloroform extracts required higher concentrations to achieve similar effects. These results are consistent with those of Akerele et al. (2008) and Afolabi et al. (2020), who also found that aqueous extracts of *Garcinia kola* were more active than those prepared with organic solvents.

The difference in potency between the extracts may be attributed not only to the solubility of bioactive compounds but also to the possibility that heat-sensitive or alcohol-degradable components such as biflavonoids (e.g., kolaviron) are better preserved in water-based preparations.

Overall, the findings of this study contribute to the growing body of evidence supporting the use of *Garcinia kola* as a potential antimicrobial agent. In light of increasing antibiotic resistance among common respiratory pathogens, plant-based alternatives like *Garcinia kola* offer promising leads for future drug development, especially in resource-limited settings.

However, it is important to note that the study was conducted *in vitro*, and the clinical efficacy and safety of these extracts remain to be determined *in vivo*. Moreover, while aqueous extracts showed the most promising results,

further studies are needed to isolate, purify, and characterize the specific phytochemicals responsible for the antimicrobial activity observed.

The results of this investigation support the traditional use of *Garcinia kola* in treating cough-related infections and highlight its potential role as a natural antimicrobial agent, particularly against *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Streptococcus pneumoniae*.

Conclusion

This study assessed the antimicrobial effects of aqueous, ethanol, and chloroform extracts of *Garcinia kola* seeds on bacterial pathogens commonly associated with cough, namely *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Haemophilus influenzae*. The phytochemical screening confirmed the presence of several bioactive compounds, including flavonoids, tannins, alkaloids, phenols, and saponins, which are likely responsible for the observed antimicrobial activity. Among the three extracts, the aqueous extract demonstrated the most potent antibacterial activity, as evidenced by larger zones of inhibition, lower Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC), and effective Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC). *Klebsiella pneumoniae* was the most frequently isolated organism and showed considerable sensitivity to the aqueous extract of *Garcinia kola*. The findings of this study support the traditional use of *Garcinia kola* in the treatment of cough and related respiratory infections. It also reinforces the potential of medicinal plants as viable alternatives or complements to synthetic antibiotics, particularly in the face of rising antimicrobial resistance.

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